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Spatial model of wildfire susceptibility using Machine Learning approaches on Rawa Aopa Watumohai National Park, Indonesia

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Abstract

Rawa Aopa National Park has experienced a severe wildfire. These fires are affected by several factors, including topography, meteorology, vegetation, and source of fire. This study uses a Machine Learning approach based on re-sampling methods (e.g. cross-validation, bootstrap, and random subsampling) to evaluate, and improve the performance of twelve basic Machine Learning algorithms: Generalized Linear Model, Support Vector Machine, Random Forest, Boosted Regression Trees, Classification And Regression Tree, Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines, Mixture Discriminate Analysis, Flexible Discriminant Analysis, Maximum Entropy, Maximum Likelihood, Radial Basis Function, and Multi-Layer Perceptron, analyze the causes of wildfires, and the correlation between variables. The model is evaluated by Area Under Curve, Correlation, True Skill Statistics, and Deviance. The evaluation results show that Bt-RF has a good performance in predicting wildfire susceptibility in TNRAW with AUC=0.98, COR=0.96, TSS=0.97, and Deviance=0.15. An area of 644.88 km² or the equivalent of 59.82% of the area is a wildfire susceptibility area with the concentration of fires occurring in the savanna ecosystem which is around 245.12 km² or the equivalent of 88.95% of the jungle zone. Among the 17 parameters that cause fires, this area is strongly influenced by Maximum Temperature, Land Use Land Cover, and Distance from Road. There is a strong correlation between soil and distance from settlements = 0.96.

Keywords

Wildfire susceptibility, Area under curve, Machine learning, Resampling method, Rawa Aopa Watumohai National Park, Conservation area

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Highlights for public administration, management and planning:

- We identify the factors that condition wildfire susceptibility and the locations of past wildfire occurrences in different conservation areas and open data sets explaining these factors. The data must be used as input for modeling with machine learning to map wildfires in conservation areas.
- The results obtained are key to a thorough assessment of wildfire susceptibility and can contribute to identifying the actions needed to increase the preparedness and resilience of protected areas.
- Research results are intended to provide valuable tools for local stakeholders and decision-makers to improve national park area planning and development strategies to mitigate the negative effects of hazards on existing activities and assets.

1 Introduction

Wildfires are a natural disaster that often occurs in various countries in the world. Approximately 4% of the global vegetation area or 19.8 million hectares of land is burned every year due

to wildfire ([Food & Agriculture Organization of the United Nations 2021](#)). Wildfires that occur in general are caused by natural factors (meteorological-climatological) such as global climate change in the form of increased drought, high air temperatures, relatively low humidity, lightning, and strong winds

as well as human action factors either intentional (burning) or negligence ([Environmental Protection Agency 2023](#); [San Miguel et al. 2017](#)). Wildfire events cause significant damage to ecosystems, infrastructure, and human life ([Food & Agriculture Organization of the United Nations 2020](#)). Wildfires also have an impact on reducing the welfare of the people of a country ([Paudel 2023](#)).

Indonesia is classified as a country that frequently experiences wildfires, especially during the dry season ([Prayoga & Koestoer 2021](#)). In the period 2018–2022, Indonesia experienced forest and land fires 2341 times with 17 people dying, 16 people being injured, 712 people suffering, 156 people being displaced, and 38 houses and 3 educational facilities were damaged ([Badan Nasional Penanggulangan Bencana 2023](#)). Wildfires that occur often hit areas with extensive peatland cover ([Nurhayati et al. 2021](#)). Rawa Aopa Watumohai National Park is one of the peat forest areas that often experiences fires, even though this area is inhabited by species endemic to the Wallacea Region and has a wide distribution of remaining topogenic peat swamps and is quite rare for Sulawesi Island ([Sugianto 2013](#)). This condition indicates that more extraordinary efforts to prevent wildfires are still urgently needed ([United Nations Environment Programme 2022](#)).

Recently, wildfire researchers and authorities have been constantly looking for new ways to reduce the fire hazard in risk areas. Efforts are underway to identify areas prone to wildfire by developing accurate wildfire hazard models and maps. A wildfire susceptibility map is a spatial model that can describe field conditions related to wildfire risk based on the formulation of wildfire trigger factors that exist at mapped locations so that it can be used for monitoring and prevention of wildfires as early as possible ([Amalina et al. 2016](#)). Therefore, studies on the occurrence of wildfires and mapping of specific wildfire hazard zones are becoming increasingly important for policy making due to wildfires that continue to occur in a recurring pattern.

Machine Learning (ML) is an approach that can be used to map wildfire susceptibility ([Mohajane et al. 2021](#); [Shao et al. 2022](#)). Wildfire natural disasters have been assessed using various methodologies such as vector machines (SVM) ([Ghorbanzadeh et al. 2019](#); [Iban & Sekertekin 2022](#)), analytical network process (ANP) ([Nunes et al. 2023](#)), random forest (RF) ([Gholamnia et al. 2020](#)), Dempster-Shafer ([Tavakkoli Piralilou et al. 2022](#)), artificial neural networks (ANN) ([Ghorbanzadeh et al. 2019](#); [Gholamnia et al. 2020](#)), decision trees ([Gholamnia et al. 2020](#)), logistic regression (LR) ([Pourghasemi 2016](#);

[Tien Bui et al. 2016](#); [Gholamnia et al. 2020](#)) convolution neural network (CNN) ([Zhang & Lim 2019](#)) and evidence belief function (EBF) ([Pourghasemi 2016](#)). These models are evaluated and compared with each other. In research conducted in the Tallgrass prairie in the US, the results of the ANN and stepwise linear regression methods were compared in estimating fuel moisture content for forest fire estimation where the ANN with stepwise linear regression (SLR) can be further used to estimate fuel moisture content. burn to estimate the fire. The assessment matrix shows ANN has higher accuracy than SLR ([Sharma et al. 2018](#)). [Kim et al. \(2019\)](#) compared RF and Maximum Entropy for predicting forest fires in South Korea. The results show the highest probability around residential areas and justify the existence of a strong correlation with human-related variables. This approach is quite good at solving non-linear problems, but its accuracy is sensitive to the quality of sample points ([Nur et al. 2023](#)) based on predetermined rules ([Akıncı & Akıncı 2023](#); [Moayedi & Khasmakhi 2023](#)). The use of ML is increasing because of its ability to efficiently extract past events without having to understand the physical processes that occurred before ([Babu et al. 2023](#); [Nur et al. 2023](#)). ML methods that are considered strong for modeling fire events such as Generalized Linear Model (GLM), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), Boosted Regression Tree (BRT), Classification and Regression Tree (CART), Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS), Mixture Discriminate Analysis (MDA), Flexible Discriminant Analysis (FDA), Maximum Entropy (MaxEnt), Maximum Likelihood (MaxLike), Radial Basis Function (RBF), and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) ([Hong et al. 2017](#); [Sachdeva et al. 2018](#); [Piao et al. 2022](#); [Shmuel & Heifetz 2022](#); [Janizadeh et al. 2023](#); [Nur et al. 2023](#); [Tan & Feng 2023](#)). These models have the advantage of including factors that are not normalized in ratio, nominal, ordinal, and interval scales ([Ferentinou & Chalkias 2013](#)). This model is used because of its ease of understanding and implementation, so it has received much attention from researchers and policy makers. Experts have tried to reduce the level of risk that might occur from models and conditioning variables ([Pham et al. 2020](#); [Shahfahad et al. 2022](#)). Pixel size exploration ([Zhang et al. 2021](#); [Tavakkoli Piralilou et al. 2022](#)) and the amount of training data ([Bjånes et al. 2021](#)) have been widely identified to understand the risks posed. However, the pre-processing and resampling stages are often neglected. This neglect triggers a class imbalance where the data that determines some

Fig. 1 Flowchart of the overall methodology

classes occurs in classes with small populations (Galar et al. 2011). The standard classification algorithm requires a large amount of data to predict classes and assumes classes with few cases are considered noise (Cieslak & Chawla 2008). This has the effect of making it difficult to separate between classes which only worsens class imbalance. Three approaches have been proposed for manipulating algorithms, data, or learning frameworks (Batista et al. 2004). Computerized statistical computation methods such as Cross-Validation (CV), Bootstrap (Bt), and Random Subsampling (RS) can be used to overcome this problem (Hastie et al. 2009; Aldiansyah & Wardani 2023, 2024) along with the proposed models. Hybridization techniques with soft computing are recommended because they can improve the quality of predictions (Fotovatikhah et al. 2018; Fu et al. 2020). The CV, Bt, and RS methods can each perform sampling with or without replacement of the original data based on samples drawn randomly into iteration B. CV and RS randomly divide the training set and validation set B times without replacing the original data, while Bt takes a sample of the same length as the original data as a training set to learn the model. Data that is partitioned and not contributed to the model is used for validation.

This study aims to predict the wildfire susceptibility in Rawa Aopa Watumahoi National Park using ML from several algorithms such as GLM, SVM, RF, BRT, CART, MARS, MDA, FDA, MaxEnt, MaxLike, RBF, and MLP. The proposed algorithm is integrated with CV, Bt, and RS to improve model performance and compare it with the Basic Model (BM). This study also evaluates the dominant factors and the correlation between the parameters and the occurrence of wildfire with the parameters.

2 Data and methods

The research methodology is outlined in the illustration in Fig. 1. The first step was to create a fire database using the FIRMS dataset from the VIIRS Aqua-Terra satellite. The 2013–2022 fire location data is then divided into training (70%) and testing (30%) datasets using the random function. After that, a spatial database consisting of factors related to wildfires was constructed and assessed using a multicollinearity analysis using training sets and layers of related factors. Calculates resampling of a weighted ensemble ML model from a standalone model. Then determine the most important set of factors for each model using the learning

Fig. 2 Study Area

vector quantization (LVQ) algorithm. Each model is calibrated and evaluated to choose the best model to predict wildfire susceptibility in conservation areas. The best model is then analyzed spatially with a conservation area zoning map.

2.1 Study Area

Rawa Aopa Watumohai National Park (TNRAW) is a conservation area which has an absolute position of 4°23'S – 121°59'E with an area based on the projection of the UTM 51 S Zone of 1,078.05 km². Rawa Aopa Watumohai National Park (TNRAW) is located in Southeast Sulawesi Province, Indonesia, and was established based on the Decree of the Minister of Forestry Number 756/Kpts-II/1990 dated 17 December 1990 (Fig. 2). Based on its bio-geographical history, this area has types of mangrove ecosystems, lowland rain forest ecosystems, savanna ecosystems, swamp ecosystems, and low mountain forest ecosystems which

are habitats for various types of wild life that need to be preserved. TNRAW has a height of up to 973 meters above sea level with the highest slope of 17 degrees. The climate of this conservation area is a tropical monsoon climate (Köppen - Am) and the annual average temperature is 18°C (Peel et al. 2007). Vegetation types in this area are distinguished based on grass types and associated vegetation (age/lontar, and savanna grasses). In the savanna area, the temperature tends to be hot, reaching 30°C-32°C which is spread over an area of 17% of the TNRAW area (Sugiarto 2013). This geographical condition is feared to trigger damage and the speed of fire spread which could affect other ecosystems.

2.2 Historical Fire Location

Making an inventory map is mandatory before making a wildfire susceptibility map (Trucchia et al. 2022). An inventory of wildfires in TNRAW was

Table 1 Information on wildfire driving factors

Category	Variable Name	Resolution	Source of Data	Reference
Topographical	Aspect	30 m	SRTM DEM	Tavakkoli Piralilou et al. (2022)
	Curvature			Mabdeh et al. (2022)
	Elevation			Ghorbanzadeh et al. (2019)
	Slope			Oliveira et al. (2021)
Meteorological	Precipitation	30 m	WorldClim	Santana et al. (2021)
	Temperature Maximum			Zhang & Lim (2019)
	Windspeed	10 m	Global Wind Atlas	Hong et al. (2019)
Environmental	Distance from Rivers	30 m	BIG	Kalantar et al. (2020)
	NDDI		Landsat 8 OLI/TIRS	Sachdeva et al. (2018)
	NDVI			Malik et al. (2021)
	NDMI			Sulova & Jokar Arsanjani (2020)
	Geology		BBSDLP	Aldiansyah et al. (2022)
	Soil			Aldiansyah et al. (2022)
Anthropological	LULC	10 m	Sentinel 2	Sharma et al. (2022)
	Distance from Roads	30 m	BIG	Tonini et al. (2020)
	Population Density	1 km	SEDAC	Shmuel & Heifetz (2022)
	Distance from Settlements	30 m	OSM	Nhongo et al. (2019)

collected from the Fire Information for Resource Management System (FIRMS) obtained from the VIIRS Aqua and Terra satellite instruments from 2013–2022. Each VIIRS active thermal pixel/fire hotspot location represents a 375 m resolution center. Only data with a 100% confidence level are used as actual hotspots for the fire inventory database to provide more precise and accurate fire location information. Non-wildfire data is obtained from field surveys in areas that do not experience wildfires. There are 188 fire points and 93 non-fire points in use. Fire point information is assumed to represent 1 event for 1 fire point. Fire point data in this study is the dependent variable for estimating the probability of wildfire. This data is saved in .csv format which contains latitude and longitude information.

2.3 Wildfire-Related Factors

The selection of independent variables, which are also called predisposing, predictor, conditioning, or driving variables, is very important in vulnerability modeling. Table 1 shows 17 variables related to wildfire susceptibility selected based on data availability and previous research (Sulova & Jokar Arsanjani 2020; Aldiansyah et al. 2022; Hosseini & Lim 2022). Variables were categorized into four categories including topography, environment, meteorology, and anthropology. This categorization aims to make cause-and-effect relationships easy to interpret. Topographic factors include As-

pect, Curvature, Elevation, and Slope. Meteorological factors related to Precipitation, Maximum Temperature, and Windspeed. Environmental factors include Distance from Rivers, Normalized Difference Drought Index (NDDI), Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Moisture Index (NDMI), Geology, and Soil. Anthropological factors include land use land cover (LULC), Distance from Roads, Population Density, and Distance from Settlements. All factors were compiled into a spatial database and resampled to a spatial resolution of 30 m. The spatial database is reclassified using the quantile method of numerical or continuous data.

Topographical factors have important effects on fire occurrence, distribution, vegetation severity, human accessibility, and local climate (Nur et al. 2022). Topographic factors are derived from the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) DEM with a spatial resolution of 30 meters. Altitude affects the severity and spread of wildfires and is related to plant composition and distribution and local climatic conditions (Castro & Chuvieco 1998). Increasing the degree of slope can increase the speed of fire distribution. Fires can spread more slowly in less steep zones and more quickly in steeper zones. Aspect indicates the direction a surface is facing and influences how much sunlight it receives (Salavati et al. 2022). Therefore, the derivative of the selected DEM data is deemed necessary to be included as a conditioning factor.

Meteorological factors regulate the life cycle of vegetation, which provides dry leaves as a source of ignition, fuel production, or a medium for spreading wildfires [Tavakkoli Piralilou et al. \(2022\)](#). Maximum precipitation and temperature data were collected from the Worldclim version 2.1 dataset for 1970–2000 with a spatial resolution of 30 m ([Fick & Hijmans 2017](#)). Rainfall affects crop patterns, and humidity levels affect the rate of fire spread. The higher the temperature, the higher the chance that the fire will ignite or continue to burn. In short, because at high temperatures, the fuel gets closer to its ignition point, and the preheated fuel will burn faster. Wind speed data was collected from the 2021 Global Wind Atlas with a spatial resolution of 10 m. Strong winds tend to blow fires away and cause them to spread quickly across the landscape. Strong winds can also carry embers further away, which can trigger new fires several kilometers from the location of the main fire source.

Factors related to the environment include Distance from Rivers, NDDI, NDVI, NDMI, Geology, and Soil. Distance from Rivers is obtained from the Geospatial Information Agency (BIG) in 2022. Distance from Rivers is related to the condition of forests and rivers that function as water sources. NDDI, NDVI, and NDMI data were collected from Google Earth Engine using a median filter for 2022. NDDI data estimates landscape dryness and surface water balance. This data is based on the Palmer drought severity index (PDSI) approach ([Zheng et al. 2021](#)). NDVI represents the state of health and humidity of vegetation ([Nhongo et al. 2019](#)). A decrease in NDVI indicates that dry vegetation affects water stress and increases the likelihood of fire. NDMI data affects the level of drought and the balance of water, and fuel and affects dead plants lying on the surface ([Sazib et al. 2021](#)). Geology and Soil were obtained from the Center for Research and Development of Agricultural Land Resources (BBSDLR) in 2016. Several studies have shown the slow production of primary plants, and soil characteristics with an abundance of charcoal, density, and a large amount of litter also exacerbate the risk of burning land ([Kasin et al. 2013](#); [Meira-Castro et al. 2015](#); [Hou et al. 2021](#)).

Anthropological factors such as LULC were collected from the Sentinel-2 10m Land Use/Land Cover times series for 2017–2021 ([Karra et al. 2021](#)). This data consists of global compilation data from Esri, Microsoft, and the Impact Observatory. Land use describes the landscape pattern, composition, and characteristics of the study area. These features can affect the ignition and distribution of fire. The Distance from road and Distance

from Settlements data are vector data that were obtained from the Geospatial Information Agency (BIG) in 2022 and Indonesia’s Open Street Map (OSM) in 2022. Meanwhile, Population Density data was obtained from the Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC) in 2020 ([CIESIN 2018](#)). Distance from Roads, Settlements, and Population Density quantify accessibility to forest areas and wildfire areas and in many cases, human activities are responsible for triggering wildfire.

2.4 Machine Learning Models

Since the early 1990s, AI has been applied in wildfire studies using neural networks and expert systems ([Jain et al. 2020](#); [Jaafari et al. 2019](#); [Kato et al. 2020](#)). Since then, the field has grown with the widespread application of several ML algorithms in wildfire prediction for wildfire preparedness, mitigation, and disaster preparedness. These developments have led to a natural evolution in the science of wildfire management to a data-centric approach that utilizes empirical and statistical models; motivated by the availability of adequate data sets that can be obtained from various sensors that provide high-quality spatiotemporal data ([Syifa et al. 2020](#); [Kato et al. 2020](#)). In addition to developing the computational efficiency of modern computer systems, ML users’ interest in wildfire prediction has increased in recent decades. The use of computational intelligence in mapping has grown over the years ([Jaafari et al. 2019](#)). As mentioned previously, in this study, the models GLM ([McCullagh 2019](#)), SVM ([Nur et al. 2023](#)), RF ([Naghibi & Pourghasemi 2015](#)), BRT ([Breiman 2017](#)), CART ([Naghibi & Pourghasemi 2015](#)), MARS ([Friedman 1991](#)), MDA ([Hair et al. 1998](#)), FDA ([Hastie et al. 1994](#)), MaxEnt ([Ebrahimi et al. 2017](#)), MaxLike ([Bonaccorso 2017](#)), RBF ([Schueremans & Gemert 2005](#)), and MLP ([Kavzoglu & Mather 2003](#)). There are adjustments to SVM and RF. ϵ -SVR type was used in this research ([Chang & Lin 2011](#)). The values, 1000 and 0.1, of the parameters σ_c and ϵ , respectively, were selected based on trial and error. The key RF parameters are the number of trees and the number of predicting factors upon which the decision tree is grown to its maximum size and then left unpruned. In this research, the values of these two parameters have been selected based on trial and error. The optimal values for these two parameters are selected namely 1000 and 4. The other methods are run with default settings. The GLM, SVM, RF, BRT, CART, MARS, MDA, FDA, MaxEnt, MaxLike, RBF, and MLP models, each run on R software using the packages ‘glm’, ‘kernlab’,

'random forest', 'gbm', 'rpart', 'earth', 'mda', 'mda', 'maxent', 'maxlike', 'rbf', and 'mlp'.

Each parameter is converted into raster data in GeoTIFF format and with wildfire occurrence data analyzed by the SDM method in R software (Naimi & Araújo 2016). The wildfire model with resampling using CV, Bt, and RS was run for 10 iterations. The wildfire susceptibility maps were each made from three different resampling techniques. The results were compared to the unprocessed model (BM) using non-resampling. The resampling technique was carried out in R software. The resulting model is a model with a sustainable vulnerability value. To obtain a wildfire hazard model, each model is classified into several classes. The quantile classification was chosen because is the most suitable for classifying facts in this study. The quantile classification can group the same number of pixels (areas) into each group. The model is classified into five classes, namely very low, low, medium, high, and very high.

2.5 Resampling Approach

2.5.1 Cross Validation

The ML modeling uses data sets that are divided into training groups and test groups. As much as 70% of the data is used for training and 30% of the data is used for testing. In each iteration of the CV process, part of the data is used for training and partly for testing. The test data is sent to the CV process and then redefined as training data in the next iteration. The dataset is used to test the model (Dieterle 2003). The CV can be performed in several ways, for example using hold-out, leave-one-out, leave-P-out, and k-fold. Making a CV in this study uses k-fold. If a training dataset is randomly split into k subsets or folds with equal sizes, each CV iteration is performed using k-1 folds as training and the remaining fold for validation. In this study, k was set to 5.

2.5.2 Bootstrap

Bootstrap is a statistical inference method that builds a sampling distribution to resample the original data (Fox 2002). The basic idea of this algorithm is to presume the sample data as a population from which several samples can be drawn. Let $W = (W_1, W_2, \dots, W_N)$ where $w_i = (w_i, y)$ with w_i denoting the explanatory variable (wildfire conditioning factors) and y denoting the response variable (wildfire susceptibility rate). The bootstrap algorithm randomly draws completely independent

samples with the replacement of the original training data Z with each drawn sample having the same length as the original data set. Bootstrap is conducted B times to produce B bootstrap samples, preserving the stochastic characteristics of the original data Z . Then B times modeling efforts tried to fit the separate bootstrap samples by reproducing the B wildfire susceptibility maps. The mean of the wildfire susceptibility predictions over the B (10 times) runs for each model was taken as a wildfire susceptibility map.

2.5.3 Random Subsampling

Random subsampling works by dividing the data into training and testing parts and repeating the process in iteration B . This technique is different from bootstrapping, random subsampling will repeat the data without replacement by involving the original data for calibration. Every time some data is used, the rest is used for model validation and this is repeated for 10 iterations. This method makes it possible to capture various relationships between predictors and response variables in constructing models.

2.6 Multicollinearity

The learning vector quantization (LVQ) algorithm was used in this study to determine the most important factors. This algorithm is considered when the perfect number of slide-triggering factors is unknown. LVQ is intended for large data by classifying the input for large data by looking for the shortest distance to the value and eliminating the noises that could potentially disrupt the convergence process in forecasting systems (Kohonen 1995). The LVQ was run in the R software. Collinearity between the layers was assessed using values at the locations of landslides in the database. Those with variance inflation factor (VIF) values greater than 10, which indicates a multicollinearity problem, were excluded from the modeling. This study also uses the Pearson Correlation method (Shi & Touge 2023) to determine the relationship between variables and variables with wildfire occurrence data. The Pearson Correlation value is in the range of -1 to 1. If there is a strong positive linear relationship between the variables, the value of r will be close to +1. If there is a strong negative linear relationship between the variables, the value of r will be close to -1. When the value of r is near 0, the linear relationship is weak or nonexistent. A value of 0 indicates that there is no linear relationship between the two variables. A correlation value

> 0.7 indicates a strong level of collinearity (Hawbaker et al. 2023). Pearson Correlation method using the following equation (Sarwono 2006):

$$r^2 = \frac{n \sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{\{n \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2\} \{n \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2\}}} \quad (1)$$

where *Corr* (r^2) is the Pearson Correlation Coefficient, n is the number of data pairs $\sum XY$ is sum of products of the paired variables, $\sum X$ is sum of the x values, $\sum Y$ is sum of the y values, $\sum X^2$ is sum of the squared x values, $\sum Y^2$ is sum of the squared y values.

2.7 Accuracy Assessment

The validity of the results of the models and pre-processing was investigated using: area under the ROC curve (AUC), correlation coefficient (COR), True Skill Statistic (TSS), and Deviance. The area under the ROC Curve (AUC) is used for the quantitative assessment of the developed integrative model. A good AUC value if the value is above 0.8 (Hai et al. 2023). TSS is an alternative to the Kappa coefficient, which, unlike the kappa statistic, is not affected by the prevalence and size of the validation data set (Allouche et al. 2006). The TSS metric indicates the ability of a model to distinguish between wildfire and non-wildfire localities. The closer to 1, the better the COR value. On the other hand, for Deviance, the closer to 0, the better the Deviance value. R was used to value generate COR, TSS, and Deviance using the following equation (Robinne et al. 2016; West et al. 2017):

$$TSS = \frac{ad - bc}{(a+c)(b+d)} = \text{Sensitivity} + \text{Specificity} - 1 \quad (2)$$

$$COR = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (WOI - \overline{WOI})(WSI - \overline{WSI})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (WOI - \overline{WOI})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (WSI - \overline{WSI})^2}} \quad (3)$$

$$D = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n \left(y_i \ln \left(\frac{y_i}{\mu_i} \right) + (1 - y_i) \ln \left(\frac{1 - y_i}{1 - \mu_i} \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

where N is the total number of samples, a and b are the number of pixels that were classified as wildfire susceptible and non-wildfire samples by the models and c is the number of known wildfires mistakenly labeled as non-wildfire areas. WOI

indicates wildfire presence ($WOI=1$) or absence ($WOI=0$), while WSI indicates sensitivity to wildfire predicted by the model. Sensitivity refers to the known wildfire pixels that were modeled as susceptible wildfire areas. Specificity, however, is the known non-wildfire pixels that were labeled as wildfire-susceptible areas by the model (West et al. 2017). If $y_i = \mu_i$ for all future observations, the D value is zero. If $y_i \neq \mu_i$ is always true, the value of D is infinite (Robinne et al. 2016).

3 Results

3.1 Wildfire Prediction

Assessment of independent variables for multicollinearity provides insight into their respective importance and position for building an optimal model. The level of relationship between two or more independent variables is measured using the VIF value. VIF values exceeding 10 are considered unsuitable for inclusion in the model. From these results, the minimum and maximum VIF are 0.52 and 1.94 respectively (Table 2). It can be seen that there are no variables that are close to the critical threshold.

Table 2 Multicollinearity assessment result

Factors	VIF
Aspect	1.17
Curvature	0.91
Elevation	1.14
Slope	0.81
Precipitation	0.99
Temperature Maximum	0.69
Wind	1.35
Distance from Rivers	1.53
NDDI	0.82
NDVI	1.38
NDMI	0.62
Geology	0.52
Soil	1.23
LULC	1.22
Distance from Roads	1.44
Population Density	0.94
Distance from Settlements	1.28

All models highlight that the highest wildfire vulnerability is in the savanna ecosystem in the southern part of the study area regardless of the geographical extent of the wildfire area. All images illustrating wildfire points correspond to high and very high wildfire classes. There are several types of sa-

Fig. 3 Wildfire susceptibility predictions by: (a) Bt-RF model, and (b) overlap with TNRAW Zoning

vanna in the TNRAW area which are differentiated based on the type of grass and vegetation associated with them, including girder grass savanna, bush savanna, reed savanna, savanna associated with agel and palmyra plants, and grass savanna. In general, the savanna vegetation in this national park has distinctive and unique characteristics, because it is an association between grasslands with agel, palmyra, and thorny bamboo plants as well as shrubs, as well as plants along the rivers that flow in the savanna. The occurrence of fires will have an impact on high CO₂ gas emissions resulting from fires and the further loss of carbon reserves in vegetation, causing higher levels of greenhouse gases to collect in the earth’s atmosphere and lead to global warming.

3.2 Assessment and Comparison

The AUC value produced by the BM model is in the range of 0.82–0.98. This shows that there is a good degree of separability between occurrence and non-occurrence classes. Based on these values, the best model is indicated by the RF model, followed by MLP, MaxEnt, BRT, SVM, MARS, CART, MDA,

GLM, FDA, RBF, and MaxLike (Table 3). The MaxLike model is the lowest-performing model compared to the other models. MaxLike is limited in its ability to accurately estimate the population means and standard deviation when the percentage of censored data is large and the sample size is small. This means that the range area and number of samples are not directly proportional in this study. The AUC curve on the CV model also shows the potential of the RF model in making accurate predictions from all wildfire training data. The CV model has a very good performance compared to the model trained with the RS technique. However, when viewed from the COR value, the Bt-RF model is superior to RF trained with different techniques. COR values imply a correlation between WOI (Occurrence = 1 and Non-occurrence = 0) and WSI values, predicted by the ML model. Higher COR values indicate close agreement between WOI and WSI and high model efficiency. If referring to the Deviance value, CV-RF can be considered for use. Referring to the AUC Curve, the BM models (GLM, MARS, MDA, and MaxEnt) can select the RS engineering option to improve the performance of the model. Meanwhile, Bt can be used on SVM,

Table 3 Model Accuracy

Algorithm	BM				CV				Bt				RS			
	i	ii	iii	iv												
GLM	0.83	0.50	0.58	0.65	0.82	0.48	0.56	0.67	0.81	0.48	0.58	0.68	0.83	0.52	0.56	0.62
SVM	0.89	0.53	0.72	0.65	0.87	0.50	0.69	0.67	0.90	0.55	0.75	0.67	0.89	0.56	0.72	0.62
RF	0.98	0.95	0.97	0.21	0.98	0.95	0.97	0.21	0.98	0.96	0.97	0.15	0.98	0.95	0.97	0.20
BRT	0.90	0.62	0.60	0.63	0.88	0.61	0.57	0.65	0.90	0.68	0.67	0.62	0.89	0.65	0.57	0.62
CART	0.85	0.67	0.59	0.53	0.83	0.63	0.57	0.57	0.78	0.66	0.55	0.70	0.85	0.68	0.60	0.52
MARS	0.88	0.57	0.61	0.57	0.88	0.57	0.58	0.58	0.89	0.61	0.64	0.56	0.89	0.59	0.61	0.56
MDA	0.85	0.50	0.56	0.72	0.84	0.50	0.56	0.70	0.83	0.49	0.56	0.75	0.86	0.53	0.59	0.66
FDA	0.83	0.49	0.57	0.67	0.80	0.47	0.54	0.70	0.80	0.47	0.54	0.71	0.81	0.51	0.55	0.68
MaxEnt	0.90	0.58	0.65	0.73	0.89	0.56	0.62	0.76	0.92	0.62	0.67	0.69	0.92	0.61	0.66	0.67
MaxLike	0.82	0.48	0.56	1.11	0.80	0.46	0.54	0.98	0.81	0.45	0.55	1.28	0.82	0.48	0.54	0.93
RBF	0.83	0.48	0.57	0.67	0.81	0.47	0.54	0.68	0.80	0.45	0.54	0.71	0.81	0.49	0.54	0.68
MLP	0.91	0.86	0.72	0.81	0.90	0.83	0.68	0.81	0.91	0.90	0.79	0.57	0.87	0.84	0.68	1.26

Note: i=AUC; ii=COR; iii=TSS; iv=Deviance

Table 4 Importance factor of wildfire using BM in AUC (%)

Factors	i	ii	ii	iv	v	vi	vii	viii	ix	x	xi	xii	
Aspect		2.59	6.70	9.38	3.96	7.05	3.23	1.34	2.67	4.17	6.44	6.47	7.02
Curvature		0.46	5.56	7.97	3.91	2.06	1.70	1.59	0.86	3.50	0.11	3.68	4.28
Elevation		2.29	2.32	3.28	1.98	17.69	34.52	1.83	1.72	35.56	0.05	2.09	1.68
Slope		0.61	3.43	6.21	1.48	0.01	0.02	22.34	0.02	7.77	0.81	2.89	7.69
Precipitation		1.83	4.15	0.23	0.74	0.87	0.02	1.59	0.02	0.98	1.46	3.68	3.56
Temperature Maximum		11.13	7.31	34.23	34.62	28.65	6.29	4.03	3.96	0.70	0.05	5.48	7.16
Wind		2.13	6.40	2.34	4.70	1.95	17.17	1.10	0.86	7.00	5.31	7.22	7.88
Distance from Rivers		0.08	1.45	0.23	0.99	3.04	4.51	0.37	0.34	1.54	2.87	8.81	5.63
NDDI		3.96	0.23	0.23	5.44	26.15	0.02	1.83	5.16	0.28	1.73	4.33	4.09
NDVI		2.59	1.22	0.94	2.47	0.87	0.85	1.47	3.40	0.98	1.62	20.16	8.13
NDMI		50.00	0.69	0.23	6.68	0.01	0.34	23.20	33.53	1.12	39.42	4.38	8.75
Geology		1.37	12.95	0.23	0.49	0.01	7.65	0.24	1.20	5.60	1.30	1.49	1.92
Soil		0.61	4.65	0.23	0.25	0.01	0.02	4.03	2.41	4.20	14.46	13.19	10.00
LULC		19.51	17.90	3.75	19.04	10.09	15.13	29.79	40.24	8.96	22.74	12.24	7.60
Distance from Roads		0.08	12.87	10.32	6.31	0.01	8.50	1.10	1.89	12.60	0.05	0.20	7.84
Population Density		0.15	7.31	0.23	0.02	0.01	0.02	1.71	0.34	0.14	0.38	2.39	4.33
Distance from Settlements		0.61	4.87	19.93	6.92	1.52	0.02	2.44	1.38	4.90	1.19	1.29	2.45

Note: i=GLM; ii=SVM; iii=RF; iv=BRT; v=CART; vi=MARS; vii=MDA; viii=FDA; ix=MaxEnt; x=MaxLike; xi=RBF; xii=MLP

MARS, MaxEnt, and MLP models. The CV technique is not recommended for all models except RF and MARS because it reduces the performance of models that are not trained with resampling techniques. The same thing happened with performance evaluation using COR on CV (except RF, MARS, and MDA). In the Bt technique, SVM, RF, BRT, MARS, MaxEnt, and MLP models can be considered using COR values. Whereas in the RS technique, all BMs can improve their performance through COR values except MLP.

In performance evaluation using TSS, the BM model can be improved using CV-RF, CV-MDA, all Bt models (except CART, FDA, MaxLike, and RBF),

RS-SVM, RS-RF, RS-CART, RS-MARS, RS-MDA, and RS-MaxEnt. Based on Deviance values, CV (MDA and MaxLike), Bt (RF, BRT, MARS, MaxEnt, and MLP) models, and all models trained with RS techniques (except MLP) can be considered to improve the accuracy of the BM model.

According to the Bt-RF model (Figure 3a), areas with very low, low, medium, high, and very high levels of wildfire susceptibility are respectively 220.87 km² (20.49%), 212.30 km² (19.69%), 214.29 km² (19.88%), 216.08 km² (20.04%), and 214.50 km² (19.90%) of the total area. Based on the TNRAW area zoning map, there are around 61.02 km² (22.14%) core zone, 13.05 km² (0.82%) exclusive

Table 5 Importance factor of wildfire using CV in AUC (%)

Factors	i	ii	iii	iv	v	vi	vii	viii	ix	x	xi	xii
Aspect	0.95	4.37	0.02	1.36	4.12	0.02	0.88	1.69	1.26	2.68	0.01	7.54
Curvature	1.07	7.44	15.36	4.99	5.20	1.60	2.50	0.85	2.18	0.41	5.21	7.39
Elevation	3.56	2.14	4.32	1.59	6.45	14.78	2.38	0.85	44.44	0.10	1.09	1.22
Slope	0.01	3.63	7.20	2.04	2.15	0.02	26.00	0.02	4.01	0.10	4.54	5.30
Precipitation	5.46	5.16	0.02	0.45	0.02	0.02	1.75	1.69	3.78	12.38	8.54	3.21
Temperature Maximum	21.49	8.46	41.27	38.80	44.81	21.19	6.25	3.38	0.11	2.68	1.57	6.47
Wind	0.59	4.18	0.02	2.04	0.02	14.60	1.00	0.21	4.01	1.24	4.78	6.78
Distance from Rivers	0.01	1.39	0.02	0.68	3.41	3.74	0.50	0.63	2.06	4.95	1.33	5.76
NDDI	2.14	2.79	0.02	11.12	18.64	0.02	1.13	2.54	0.57	9.29	9.33	7.65
NDVI	2.26	0.28	4.80	3.63	0.02	14.78	1.75	3.38	0.34	0.10	4.18	8.61
NDMI	52.83	0.84	1.44	9.30	0.02	0.02	24.38	55.37	0.46	9.70	17.99	3.16
Geology	0.12	14.50	0.02	0.02	0.02	6.59	0.25	0.21	7.45	1.24	9.39	4.94
Soil	0.24	4.00	0.02	0.23	0.02	0.02	3.25	2.54	4.35	9.08	0.61	6.88
LULC	9.02	12.37	1.44	12.25	15.06	6.05	19.13	23.67	5.38	45.72	21.56	12.28
Distance from Roads	0.24	12.83	10.08	5.33	0.02	14.24	3.75	2.75	14.55	0.10	4.54	6.37
Population Density	0.01	8.93	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	2.25	0.21	0.11	0.10	3.63	4.33
Distance from Settlements	0.01	6.69	13.92	6.13	0.02	2.31	2.88	0.02	4.93	0.10	1.70	2.09

Note: i=GLM; ii=SVM; iii=RF; iv=BRT; v=CART; vi=MARS; vii=MDA; viii=FDA; ix=MaxEnt; x=MaxLike; xi=RBF; xii=MLP

zone, 52.26 km² (18.97%) utilization zone, 55.64 km² (20.19%) rehabilitation zone, 245.12 km² (88.95%) jungle zone, and 14.29 km² (5.19%) traditional zone which has a level of vulnerability to wildfire (Figure 3b).

3.3 Importance of Variable

The role of parameters in causing wildfires varies from one region to another. Therefore, it is very important to evaluate and validate the data before using it as input in Machine Learning. In the BM model (Table 4), there are no parameters that cause wildfire that have the same level of similarity among all the selected models. All focus models highlight the LULC parameter as one of the three parameters that contribute to the occurrence of wildfires in TNRAW (except RF, CART, and MLP). The Maximum Temperature parameter is a parameter that contributes to the GLM, RF, BRT, and CART models. The CART, MARS, and MaxEnt models consider Elevation to be an important parameter. In the SVM, RF, MARS, and MaxEnt models, Distance from Road is the most important parameter. Meanwhile, the MDA, FDA, MaxLike, and MLP models highlight the NDMI parameter as the most important parameter.

In the CV model (Table 5), the most important parameter for the CV model is Temperature Maximum (except SVM, MaxEnt, MaxLike, RBF, and MLP). The LULC parameters were assessed as important by the CV models (except RF, MARS, and MaxEnt). Models that have the same level of param-

eter importance are BRT and CART, namely Maximum Temperature, NDDI, and LULC. In addition, the MDA and FDA models also show the same thing by highlighting the Temperature Maximum, NDMI, and LULC parameters as important parameters. Similar to the BM model, the model trained with the CV technique also predominantly highlights Temperature, LULC, and NDDI. The Bt model (Table 6), also has varying levels of importance from all models. But it also still highlights the Temperature Maximum and LULC parameters. Likewise, the RS model has a slightly different pattern to the CV where the contributing parameters are Maximum Temperature, NDDI, and Distance from Roads (Table 7). However, if we refer to the percentage of AUC values, the three parameters that contribute (percentage ≠ 0.00) in building the BM model and the model trained using the resampling technique are consistent in the parameters Temperature Maximum, LULC, and Distance from Roads.

3.4 Multicollinearity

Meteorological, environmental, and anthropological aspects play an important role in this research because several parameters have a strong correlation with other variables (Figure 4). Slope has a strong correlation between Precipitation (0.72) and Temperature Maximum (0.72). Lowlands are associated with climatic conditions that favor fire vulnerability. In this study, wildfire occurred in the lowlands with low rainfall. This lowland

Table 6 Importance factor of wildfire using Bt in AUC (%)

Factors	i	ii	iii	iv	v	vi	vii	viii	ix	x	xi	xii
Aspect	0.10	5.01	0.01	5.86	0.09	0.19	0.14	0.23	3.29	0.80	0.68	8.67
Curvature	0.21	2.70	0.01	1.42	10.90	0.19	2.89	0.23	0.82	0.50	2.56	4.95
Elevation	1.67	4.24	0.01	3.01	1.21	0.19	11.43	0.94	33.98	6.78	2.04	3.41
Slope	1.46	4.24	12.48	7.78	5.03	0.19	26.19	0.47	5.66	0.25	4.60	3.91
Precipitation	4.18	6.17	0.01	4.69	0.09	0.19	1.74	1.88	2.68	18.94	7.41	2.80
Temperature Maximum	9.61	2.31	4.99	18.20	57.50	16.07	8.68	2.35	0.01	5.17	2.73	1.99
Wind	2.51	4.53	0.01	6.90	0.09	0.19	4.49	1.41	1.85	6.58	6.39	7.52
Distance from Rivers	0.63	2.22	24.97	2.34	8.85	7.29	0.29	0.94	4.02	2.81	9.28	8.44
NDDI	1.46	1.93	0.01	13.43	2.14	0.19	0.43	0.47	0.01	18.33	8.60	3.41
NDVI	4.60	3.09	0.01	2.93	0.09	0.19	0.87	1.41	1.65	0.65	5.03	8.93
NDMI	62.70	2.31	0.01	2.93	1.49	0.19	19.83	65.73	0.01	14.16	19.85	2.95
Geology	0.10	8.49	0.01	0.84	0.09	0.19	0.14	0.23	4.53	2.46	2.04	10.51
Soil	3.34	7.33	0.01	1.51	0.09	13.46	1.74	10.33	7.93	3.16	8.43	6.48
LULC	6.69	19.48	2.50	2.76	6.24	12.52	13.31	12.21	7.82	10.20	9.45	8.24
Distance from Roads	0.42	6.94	29.96	17.57	0.09	19.07	2.17	0.47	16.99	2.31	4.09	4.79
Population Density	0.10	15.72	0.01	1.59	0.09	0.19	1.01	0.23	0.41	4.47	1.87	5.87
Distance from Settlements	0.21	3.28	24.97	6.23	5.87	29.53	4.63	0.47	8.34	2.41	4.94	7.13

Note: i=GLM; ii=SVM; iii=RF; iv=BRT; v=CART; vi=MARS; vii=MDA; viii=FDA; ix=MaxEnt; x=MaxLike; xi=RBF; xii=MLP

Table 7 Importance factor of wildfire using RS in AUC (%)

Factors	i	ii	iii	iv	v	vi	vii	viii	ix	x	xi	xii
Aspect	1.50	5.36	4.05	0.48	0.21	49.74	1.13	1.94	2.96	4.72	8.80	5.48
Curvature	0.95	6.14	9.11	58.76	1.88	1.37	5.65	0.58	1.77	0.07	8.43	6.09
Elevation	9.96	1.36	0.13	0.19	1.88	2.35	7.16	2.48	33.00	0.07	8.16	4.08
Slope	0.55	1.46	18.99	1.82	4.08	0.01	37.85	0.45	6.40	5.99	4.54	5.73
Precipitation	1.36	4.97	0.13	0.67	0.10	0.01	3.58	0.27	0.59	0.70	1.85	3.53
Temperature Maximum	40.38	6.82	31.14	15.41	41.88	19.90	16.57	9.49	0.20	0.70	11.12	5.00
Wind	0.68	3.51	3.54	2.87	0.10	3.40	0.56	0.50	4.14	9.51	0.37	5.18
Distance from Rivers	0.07	1.27	0.13	0.67	0.10	1.70	2.26	0.58	1.87	2.54	4.36	4.51
NDDI	0.14	5.46	0.13	3.73	8.90	1.13	1.13	1.57	0.79	33.45	11.49	10.36
NDVI	2.32	2.83	5.06	2.58	1.47	2.35	1.32	0.21	0.79	0.56	1.85	5.91
NDMI	36.29	1.95	0.13	3.92	0.10	0.01	5.65	73.82	0.49	5.21	13.90	4.08
Geology	0.68	2.73	0.13	0.48	0.10	4.85	1.32	0.50	6.31	0.28	2.87	3.35
Soil	0.55	3.90	0.13	0.29	0.10	1.29	2.82	1.20	15.27	12.68	2.97	1.35
LULC	4.37	24.85	0.76	2.78	36.75	1.62	5.84	5.58	5.71	14.44	6.02	7.56
Distance from Roads	0.07	15.20	12.91	2.68	0.94	6.55	0.75	0.33	10.84	0.07	7.88	13.16
Population Density	0.07	7.02	0.13	0.10	0.10	0.01	1.51	0.25	0.20	7.75	3.52	4.33
Distance from Settlements	0.07	5.17	13.42	2.58	1.26	3.72	4.90	0.25	8.67	1.27	1.85	10.30

Note: i=GLM; ii=SVM; iii=RF; iv=BRT; v=CART; vi=MARS; vii=MDA; viii=FDA; ix=MaxEnt; x=MaxLike; xi=RBF; xii=MLP

area is also covered with savanna ecosystems such as bushes and occupies the driest area in this region. The vegetation is usually lower and the soil reflectivity is greater compared to plants. Sparsely vegetated shrubland vegetation reflects greater amounts of incoming radiation than grasslands with lower albedo. There is also a strong correlation between NDMI and Geology (0.90). Cooling occurs in this region when water is lost from the soil and plants because energy is lost when the water goes from liquid to gas. This energy loss depends

on the physical properties of the soil and water content, the area of leaves in the plant canopy, the capacity of the air mass in the canopy to mix with the air above it.

Other strong correlations also occur, such as Soil to LULC (0.76), Distance from Road (0.80), and Distance from Settlement (0.96). Differences in land cover can change the surface energy balance. At a local scale, increased heat storage associated with loss of soil moisture and changes in soil surface properties in shrublands may increase water stress

Aspect	Curvature	Elevation	Slope	Precipitation	Temperature Maximum	Windspeed	Distance from River	NDDI	NDVI	NDMI	Geology	Soil	LULC	Distance from Road	Population Density	Distance from Settlements	Occurrences
-0.06																	
-0.08	0.06																
-0.29	0.08	-0.01															
-0.08	0.11	-0.13	0.72														
-0.09	0.16	-0.12	0.72	0.43													
0.18	-0.09	0.05	-0.52	-0.74	-0.60												
0.00	-0.01	0.08	0.21	-0.02	0.09	0.08											
-0.01	0.04	0.03	0.18	0.22	0.14	-0.31	-0.27										
0.12	0.02	-0.02	-0.27	-0.28	-0.06	0.39	0.34	-0.04									
-0.15	0.03	0.02	0.47	0.43	0.20	-0.56	-0.22	0.15	-0.77								
-0.16	0.04	0.04	0.45	0.43	0.20	-0.58	-0.38	0.13	-0.89	0.9							
0.11	-0.01	0.02	-0.52	-0.63	-0.29	0.65	0.37	-0.43	0.37	-0.38	-0.5						
0.04	-0.01	0.04	-0.39	-0.50	-0.15	0.58	0.47	-0.33	0.42	-0.36	-0.48	0.76					
0.01	-0.13	-0.03	-0.51	-0.47	-0.31	0.64	0.28	-0.21	0.59	-0.78	-0.80	0.80	0.44				
-0.11	0.14	-0.11	0.50	0.23	0.87	-0.55	-0.13	0.05	-0.23	0.41	0.37	-0.08	0.02	-0.40			
-0.03	-0.14	0.05	-0.08	-0.23	-0.06	0.29	0.44	-0.36	0.30	-0.17	-0.33	0.96	0.53	0.32	0.08		
-0.17	0.09	-0.14	0.19	0.01	0.31	-0.35	-0.53	0.18	-0.38	0.38	0.48	-0.23	-0.22	-0.44	0.06	-0.28	

Fig. 4 The correlation between variables and variables with wildfire occurrence

and limit photosynthesis in grasses, thereby reducing productivity, biomass, and vegetation production. This happened in this region. The movement and activities of humans, animals, and vehicles on the road provide many opportunities for intentional or unintentional fires. The conservation area in the study area is traversed by a primary collector road that cuts through most of the savanna ecosystem, making it possible for local communities and visitors to cause wildfires. Several plant species are a source of food for the population in this area. When collecting plants, people carelessly throw away matches and burn cigarette butts, which is the main cause of wildfires in the study area. Forest areas near settlements are more prone to fires because residents' residential/cultural practices can cause accidental fires. Very few settlements are located within forests in the study area, but they may still be the cause of some wildfires.

4 Discussion

Vulnerability mapping with appropriate assessment techniques is an important component for preventing and mitigating damage from wildfires. A fire inventory database is essential for the proper construction of fire vulnerabilities. Aqua and Terra

Satellite imagery is suitable for obtaining wildfire incident data inventories due to its availability, cost and time efficiency, independence from field work, and better coherent fire identification. Integrated with the non-fire perimeter from the Southeast Sulawesi BKSDA strengthens fire predictions in the study area. The selection of appropriate conditioning factors also needs to be determined precisely to reduce the accuracy of quantity estimates that are feared to weaken the significance of the regression model. So the first step to ensuring a reliable wildfire susceptibility map from the model is to evaluate possible relationships between each of the 17 wildfire conditioning factors considered. Because there was no serious linear relationship between any of the explanatory data based on the estimated VIF values, 17 variables were included in building the model.

We present SDM using basic algorithms and applying resampling techniques with Machine Learning to increase its accuracy in identifying areas susceptible to fire in TNRAW, Indonesia. The training: testing ratio separation is 70:30 of the data set. The number of iterations is set to 10, it turns out that from the 168th point (70% of the available data) onwards, the fluctuation of the gamma value and the standard error have decreased. This means that selecting more or fewer data samples for model

training does not affect model performance. All models produced showed good results with an AUC score greater than 0.8 (except Bt-CART). Bt-RF performance is the best with AUC=0.98, COR= 0.96, TSS=0.97, and Deviance=0.15. The model trained by the resampling technique achieves higher performance than the base model. [Eslami et al. \(2021\)](#) and [Trucchia et al. \(2022\)](#) also reported the same result where the RF model has good accuracy in modeling wildfire susceptibility. The RF algorithm can find the best properties among a random set of properties, rather than looking for the most important properties when separating 'nodes'. This also creates variations and aims to produce the best model. The RF works by considering only one sub-feature when dividing the 'nodes' in this study. RF has the advantages of a relatively fast resolution process, does not overfit with an increasing number of trees, and has better accuracy than other models ([Breiman 2001](#)). The Bt technique plays an important role in duplicating limited samples and when the population distribution is unknown. Bt is more flexible with categorical, ordinal, or continuous variable types. Bt also nicely handles outliers and skewed better than parametric methods. When bootstrapping is used in some classification techniques such as RF, it can lead to the phenomenon of black box models where the results of the operations performed cannot be fully explained because of their complexity. So it is important to evaluate the prediction map of RF when combined with this technique.

The results showed that there was no significant multicollinearity and all related factors used in this study had a significant effect on the vulnerability of wildfire in TNRAW. This means that the role of wildfire conditioning factors will vary from region to region and we should be able to conclude that it is a function of the properties of the sample data. To prove this claim, this study uses the BT algorithm together with the GLM model to model wildfire susceptibility using different samples during $B = 10$ simulations. In each round, each random sample was taken with the replacement of the original data and used to analyze the relationship between wildfire conditioning factors and wildfire events using the GLM model based on AUC and COR criteria. So each different process variable is identified as the most important influencing factor. For example, the variables NDDI and Temperature Maximum are the main influencing factors in the 6th run, while NDVI and precipitation have a more important role in the 8th run. Generally, for 10 runs, the most important variables are NDMI, LULC, and Maximum Temperature ([Table 5](#)). To determine

the most influential factor, the average value of variable importance over $B = 10$ runs is calculated. The SDM method also reveals that the spatial relationship between each factor and the occurrence of wildfire is not randomly distributed throughout the conservation area. The largest fire area is centered on the savanna ecosystem. Vegetation density varies across the landscape and low vegetation densities are concentrated in savanna fields which are more easily burned. This finding was also reported by [Bustillo Sánchez et al. \(2021\)](#), [Tonini et al. \(2021\)](#), [Chicas et al. \(2022\)](#) and [Lacerda et al. \(2022\)](#) that savanna is the land cover that most frequently experiences fires. Land use determines the type, amount, structure, and continuity of vegetation, with fuel characteristics and fuel continuity being variables that affect wildfire characteristics, such as probability, distribution, severity, and frequency, by providing different amounts and conditions of fuel for different times. Nature conservation areas with savanna ecosystems have a high to very high probability of wildfire in the prediction map made. In most of the very high wildfire susceptibility classes, this study detected lower NDVI values. This pattern is most likely influenced by weather where higher temperatures encourage slower plant growth or possibly death and become a source of fuel. Fuel load is described as a forest type such as the amount of leaf litter, small branches, fallen bark, and accumulated on the landscape. In general, the greater the fuel load, the hotter and more intense the fire. A fuel that is concentrated but loosely compacted will burn more quickly than a fuel source that is highly dense or dispersed. Smaller fuels such as branches, twigs, and leaf litter will burn quickly, especially if the fuel is dry. Especially in the dry season, savanna ecosystems such as reeds become very dry and easily catch fire. Through low fuel moisture content, increasing the likelihood of fires occurring over a wider and closer area through undergrowth is more likely to occur which tends to result in similar vegetation cell values within one unit of burned land. Friction between dry reed leaves and supported by the wind triggers the ignition of a fire. Even so, the behavior of throwing cigarette butts is still the main trigger for fires in TNRAW considering that the location of the burning incident is a route that is often traversed by visitors. Although not stated explicitly, in some runs vegetation density is one of the most important variables, but the average value is not always constant and ultimately makes it less important in the final results. Additionally, it is likely that the contribution of greenness values is the same for trees or large shrubs that were

not exposed to fire because NDVI is indiscriminate in this case. Therefore, NDVI should not be averaged over all fire units considering that variations in canopy openness affect the values. Fires that occur in the savanna are high intensity and occur in the understory, so the impact is quite large throughout this vegetation. To address this fire heterogeneity, we recommend dividing fire units into smaller sub-units and conducting field tests, which were not included in this study.

In the case of a high Pearson Correlation value among two factors, the simplest method is to delete one of the factors from the dataset and repeat the analysis (Dai & Lee 2001). While Pearson's Correlation coefficient method provides some positive insights, a few results were unexpected. Land and Distance from Settlement are functions that are governed by the environment and humans and thus, a higher correlation between these factors. However, regarding the interpretation of correlations, the following points should be considered:

1. A correlation of zero indicates absolutely no linear relationship between those two variables whatsoever. Pearson quantifies statistical association in terms of a straight line (Xu & Deng 2017). Pearson, however, does not eliminate the potential for some non-linear relationship between those two variables. Hence, two variables that may be highly associated with one another may produce a Pearson's Correlation coefficient value of zero. Thus, a Pearson score of zero, between two variables, neither means no association nor that one cannot predict one of the pair from the other;
2. Correlation can be extremely reactive to the influence of outliers; one extraordinary observation may have a significant impact on a particular correlation. A quick survey of the scatterplot facilitates the detection of outliers (Winter et al. 2016), and
3. Correlations are not always causally related (Price 2000), nor are the relationships fully reciprocal in that the same association does not apply in both directions. For example, a causal relation will exist between two events where the first causes the occurrence of the second. In simple terms, the first event becomes known as the cause, while the second event becomes the effect. Alternatively, correlations between two variables are not necessarily based on causation. Hence, the Pearson method has its limitations.

In this study, several correlations have been impacted by outliers, unequal variance, non-normality,

and nonlinearity (Winter et al. 2016). The method is most successfully applied where both variables in the pair express normal distribution (Mukaka 2012).

As discussed above, the prediction of wildfire susceptibility depends on the selection of wildfire conditioning factors, and both are a function of the sample data points used for modeling. All investigations on wildfire modeling use one-time data splitting for wildfire modeling and prediction. Regarding the nonlinear enhancement between wildfire influencing factors and wildfire occurrence in large-scale areas, the results would be expected to bias the predictions for prediction of wildfire susceptibility by applying a one-time data split training and validation set. This is due to the limited information used to project wildfire which is biased. The proposed model based on the CV, Bt, and RS algorithms provides sufficient information for learning models using different sample points. Using this model, various kinds of nonlinear associations between predictors and predictors lead to unbiased predictions. For the sake of limited processing speed, $B = 10$ resampling runs were used in this study. Although the results of this study are promising, for areas with limited environmental data and increasing nonlinearity between predictors and wildfire events the number of RS samples should be increased to an adequate number.

In this study, the factors influencing fire vulnerability can be effective in evaluating wildfire mapping for other areas when the anthropological aspects and model input parameters are the same where environmental and meteorological differences must be considered. In addition, the proposed method can be used efficiently to obtain wildfire susceptibility maps for areas with little data and wide area coverage. The method used in this study can be used for other study areas, as well as for mapping the probability analysis of other natural disasters such as landslides, river floods, and erosion. The requirements are an inventory map that describes the history and location of previous fire hotspots, a set of relevant conditioning factors (thematic maps), and a spatial analysis to process the resampling technique. Our results can also be extended to map phenomena related to landslide triggers (heavy rains or after droughts, earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, shoreline changes, and loss of vegetation). The vulnerability map produced in this study only represents wildfire susceptibility zones in conservation areas such as TNRAW. In addition, this research will improve understanding of the evaluation process and consistency in decision-making for wildfire

preparedness activities (e.g. zoning of conservation areas) in the future.

5 Conclusions

This research explores various algorithms to find an accurate and reliable algorithm for detecting areas prone to wildfire. Twelve ML algorithms namely GLM, SVM, RF, BRT, CART, MARS, MDA, FDA, MaxEnt, MaxEnt, RBF, and MLP with the resampling method were used in this study. These results cannot be generalized to predictions of wildfire in other parts of the world with certainty because the behavior patterns of variables affecting wildfire vary by region. The Bt algorithm is considered to perform better than the CV and RS algorithms in the work evaluation. Among the Bt models, Bt-RF shows satisfactory performance. The sensitivity analysis of the response variable to various wildfire conditioning factors identified different conditioning factors with varying degrees of importance for each simulation which justifies the use of the proposed model for modeling wildfire susceptibility. Referring to the average value it was found that Temperature Maximum, LULC, and Distance from Road contributed to the wildfire phenomenon in this study. Future research should include the full set of factors available in wildfire prediction. The role of pixel size and use of wildfire zones as surrogates for wildfire points should be explored along with resampling methods. Further evaluation is also needed for each resampling method for the number of low, medium, and high risk locations generated at each location in the same area. In this way, the effect of resampling on data sample size and model efficiency can be reviewed in cases where the sample population is smaller. The largest correlation occurs between the Soil and Distance from Settlement variables, meaning that the occurrence of wildfire in this area is strongly influenced by human intentional elements supported by soil conditions. The importance of other factors differs between models. Based on the zoning map of the TNRAW area, there are approximately 61.02 km² (22.14%) core zone, 13.05 km² (0.82%) exclusive zone, 52.26 km² (18.97%) utilization zone, 55.64 km² (20.19%) rehabilitation zone, 245.12 km² (88.95%) jungle zone, and 14.29 km² (5.19%) traditional zone have a level of wildfire susceptibility. Future research should include evaluations and be consistent with regulations. Future zoning changes must follow the rules and regulations that have been formulated in the planning

stage. This aims to realize good policy formulation and maintain important species in this area.

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